

Characterization and beneficiation of carbonaceous material in Indian fly ash

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Abstract : Millions of tons of coal fly ash are produced in India every year. The developed world is now exploring all possible ways of recycling this waste so as to avoid environmental problems that may arise from waste accumulation. The presence of excessive carbon in pulverized fly ash is regarded as a serious issue as it is an important power plant efficiency indicator. With the possibility of landfill taxes, quantity and quality of fly ash is a matter of greater concern. Variable or unacceptable carbon contents in fly ash adversely affect ash utilization. Consequently, there is a need to be able to remove carbon from pulverized fly ash streams. In the present paper, carbon removal has been shown to be possible by treatment of high carbon fly ash by flotation. A wide range of characterization of fly ash was done and this was further subjected to flotation to observe the effect of collector and frother on the recovery of carbon.

Keywords : Carbon, fly ash, characterization, recovery, flotation.

Introduction

Fly ash is the fine powder formed from the mineral matter in coal, consisting of the noncombustible matter in coal plus a small amount of carbon that remains from incomplete combustion. Fly ash is generally light tan in color and consists mostly of silt-sized and clay-sized glassy spheres. Properties of fly ash vary significantly with coal composition and plant-operating conditions.

Indian fly ash contains higher percentage of carbon, which makes it unsuitable for the high value market because this carbon has strong tendency to adsorb air entrainment admixture which is used to stabilize concrete by absorbing air bubbles. Carbon levels have always been important for ash marketing as well as combustion efficiency consideration.

The presence of unburnt carbon in Indian fly ash is mainly due to the type and rank of coal. Complete combustion of coal in a utility boiler is a function of three parameters : oxygen, temperature and time¹. If there is sufficient oxygen present to combine with all of the car-

bon; if there is sufficient time and temperature for thorough mixing and combustion to occur, then the level of unburnt carbon in the ash will be small. Most low NO_x combustion devices delays fuel air mixing, thus coal will burn at lower temperature for a longer period of time². In theory there is enough air for complete combustion but in practice there is almost always some unburned carbon present.

When the fly ash does not possess desired properties for the product, it is possible to beneficiate it to achieve the desired properties. Consequently, there is a clear need to recover this excess unburnt carbon and to establish environmental and cost effective strategies for the use of these carbonaceous waste products in order to increase the utility of fly ash.

Here an attempt has been made to separate unburnt carbon in Indian fly ash. With the purpose of development of new applications of these unburnt carbons they have been physically collected from high LOI fly ashes and should be characterized properly.

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Experimental

About 100 kg each of fly ash samples were collected from Bokaro Thermal Power Station (BTPS), located in eastern India in the state of Jharkhand and from Dishergarh Thermal Power Station (DTPS) located in the state of West Bengal respectively. These samples have been used for the experiments.

Characterization of fly ash :

Investigations have been carried out to study the physicochemical properties of both samples i.e. BTPS fly ash and DTPS fly ash.

Chemical characterization :

The chemical analysis was mainly carried out using Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS), Model Spectra A10 plus of USA made. Results have been shown in Table 2.

Chemical compositions of the ashes as determined by XRF analysis are presented in Table 3.

Mineralogical characterization :

The mineralogical composition of the fly ashes was determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a PW 1729 X-ray generator, which was attached with Goniometer model PW 1820 of Philips and PW 1710 diffract meter control device. The XRD patterns are given in Fig. 2.

Physical characterization :

The physical characterization of fly ashes included particle size analysis, BET surface area determinations and proximate analysis. These parameters were selected as they have an important influence on the recovery of unburnt carbon from fly ash as well as for other structural and chemical applications.

Size analysis has been done by two methods; sieve size analysis and particle size analysis. The sieving of each of the fly ash sample (BTPS and DTPS) was carried out using a set of sieves viz. 212, 180, 125, 108, 90, 63 microns. The results are given in Table 4.

Particle size analysis of the samples was carried out using CILAS 1064 liquid model particle size analyzer. BTPS fly ash and DTPS fly ash were analyzed and results are shown in Table 5.

Surface area analysis has been given in Table 6. The results of proximate analysis have been given in Table 7.

Recovery of carbon-enriched part from fly ash :

A flotation machine of modified Denver type having a 6 L capacity cell (indigenously fabricated in the Department of Fuel and Mineral Engineering, Indian School of Mines) was used for experimental work. The flotation machine was fitted with an overhead water tank, placed adjacent to the cell to maintain a constant pulp level in the cell during experimentation. A variable speed froth scrapper was provided to remove the froth from the top surface of the froth zone automatically during experimentation. The machine designed was a self-aerated type and the air sucked by the impeller varies with the speed of the rotor. Hence to keep the aeration rate at a constant level (L/min) a speed controller was provided to the cell. A number of preliminary experiments were performed to identify the appropriate levels of variables for conducting the flotation experiments. On the basis of the results of these preliminary tests, the levels of variables for main experiments were fixed during the tests and which are as given in Table 1. A ray diagram of set up used is shown in Fig. 1.

Results and discussion

Chemical characterization :

A perusal of Table 2 indicates that the chemical compositions of BTPS fly ash and DTPS fly ashes are different from each other.

As it is clear from the table, the percentage of Cu, Co, Mn, Pb and Zn is negligible in the BTPS sample. Similar in case of DTPS fly ash but the amount of Fe, Co, Mn, Pb and Zn are higher and Cu, Cr and Mg content is less. The difference in elemental composition may be due to the difference in the source of coal being used.

The XRF analysis of BTPS and DTPS fly ash presented in Table 3 show that the percentage of CaO is very low in BTPS fly ash while in case of DTPS fly ash; it is appreciable at 5.6%. This indicates that BTPS fly ash will not have any cementitious property on its own, while DTPS fly ash may exhibit this property to some extent. However the presence of appreciable amount of unburnt carbon in these samples makes the ashes unsuitable as pozzolanic material. The composition of BTPS fly ash and DTPS fly ash is predominantly siliceous followed by the insoluble oxides of aluminium, iron and negligible

Table 1. Levels of the variables and parameters in flotation experiments

Levels of variables kept constant :					
Sample	Variable	Level maintained			
BTPS	Impeller speed	1200 rpm			
	Pulp density	10% solids by wt (350 g fly ash + 5810 cc water)			
	Depressant dosage (Na-silicate)	1 kg/ton of solids			
	Conditioning time	Reagent used			Time (min)
		For depressant (sodium silicate)			3.0
For frother (MIBC ^b)				1.0	
	For collector (kerosene oil)			1.0	
	Froth collection time	1.0 min			
DTPS	Impeller speed	1200 rpm			
	Pulp density	10% solids by wt (350 g fly ash + 5810 cc water)			
	Depressant dosage (sodium silicate)	1 kg/ton of solids			
	Conditioning time	Reagent used			Time (min)
		For depressant (sodium silicate)			3.0
For frother (MIBC ^b)				1.0	
	For collector (kerosene oil)			1.0	
	Collection time ^a	2.0 min			
Levels of variables varied :					
BTPS	Collector dosage (kg/ton) of solids	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.75
	Frother dosage (kg/ton) of solids	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00
DTPS	Collector dosage (kg/ton) of solids	1.50	1.75	2.00	2.25
	Frother dosage (kg/ton) of solids	0.75	1.00	1.25	1.50

^aArrived after standardization of the trial tests.

^bMethyl-iso-butyl-carbinol.

Table 2. Chemical analysis of fly ash sample

Sample	Chemical analysis in percentage (%)							
	Cu	Fe	Cr	Co	Mn	Mg	Pb	Zn
BTPS feed	0.026	0.21	0.089	0.040	0.014	0.107	0.030	0.016
DTPS feed	0.020	0.68	0.053	0.051	0.030	0.020	0.046	0.042

Table 3. Results of XRF analysis

Chemical constituent	BTPS fly ash (%)	DTPS fly ash (%)
SiO ₂	51.41	50.4
Al ₂ O ₃	25.62	19.1
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.89	13.1
MnO	-	0.121
MgO	0.23	0.803
CaO	0.42	5.6
Na ₂ O	0.13	0.17
K ₂ O	0.97	3.58
TiO ₂	1.74	3.8
P ₂ O ₅	0.61	2.11

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the flotation set-up used in experimental work.

amount of phosphorous pentoxide and titanium oxide. The appreciable difference in the composition of the two

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of BTPS fly ash and DTTPS fly ash respectively.

Table 4. Sieve size analysis of as received fly ash sample

Size range (μ)	BTPS fly ash		DTTPS fly ash	
	Wt. (%)	Ash (%)	Wt. (%)	Ash (%)
+212	0.40	61.12	20.7	52.19
-212 + 180	0.16	63.61	3.14	79.04
-180 + 125	23.15	67.81	10.8	76.62
-125 + 108	3.21	73.09	5.5	82.16
-108 + 90	2.49	80.42	4.7	80.71
-90 + 63	11.65	87.41	12.8	83.04
-63	58.92	93.09	40.6	84.19
Composite	99.98	85.42	98.24	74.68

Table 5. Particle size distribution of all the fly ash samples

Sample/Cumulative value (%)	Particle size (μ)									
	0.04	0.90	2.40	4.60	9.00	23.00	30.00	66.00	130.0	400.0
BTPS as received sample	0.10	2.25	4.25	5.99	8.15	16.57	22.11	55.34	90.54	100
DTTPS as received sample	0.03	0.69	1.46	2.10	2.80	5.36	7.27	25.68	62.56	100

ashes revealed by the ash analysis is a pointer to the nature of the two ash samples. While BTPS ash is pure fly ash, the DTTPS ash is in fact Coal Combustion Byproduct (CCB). This fact and the difference in the coals used for burning as well as the difference in the technology adopted for the combustors may be responsible for the significant difference in the chemical composition of the two ashes.

Mineralogical characterization :

Fly ash can be approximated as an aluminosilicate and can be used like other minerals. The amorphous aluminosilicate nature of fly ash makes the chemical nature of fly ash difficult to characterize, but also very versatile³.

Crystalline compounds identified by X-ray powder diffraction include quartz and mullite, which is present in greater amount in both the sets of samples i.e. BTPS as well as DTTPS. Compositions of both ash samples are very similar to each other exhibiting almost equal amount of quartz and mullite. They exhibit a peak of highest intensity at the 25° to 30° 2-theta regions. This indicates the presence of quartz in all these samples. Quartz in fly ash originates from clay and silt in the coal that is not fluxed by other inorganic materials. Mullite is found to be the principal aluminosilicates phase in the fly ash sample under study.

The mineralogy of fly ash is closely related to the minerals entrained in the coal and several different minerals have been identified as part of fly ash. The main phases are glass, mullite, quartz, magnetite and hematite and anhydrite.

Physical characterization :

Sieve size analysis :

Particle size analysis shows that DTTPS sample contains larger particles (50% larger than 102.76 μ m) than BTPS fly ash (50% larger than 60.25 μ m). This also may be explained due to difference in the mechanism of formation of the two ashes.

Table 6. Surface area of fly ash sample

Sample	BTPS (as received fly ash)	DTPS (as received fly ash)
Surface area (m ² /g)	3.1153	2.1311

Table 7. Results of proximate analysis of ash samples

Sample	Moisture (%)	Volatile matter (%)	Ash (%)	Fixed carbon (%)	LOI (%)
BTPS fly ash	1.43	2.44	88.61	7.52	11.39
DTPS fly ash	0.71	4.9	75.81	18.58	24.19

Surface area analysis :

Surface area of the as received fly ash is given in Table 6. This range is in accordance with the usual surface area measurements in fly ashes⁴.

Proximate analysis :

The results of proximate analysis of different samples are presented in Table 7. A study of the table show that the moisture content of BTPS fly ash is 1.43, which is moderate value of moisture content while the moisture content of DTPS fly ash is 0.71, which is quite low. The moisture content depends on the type of disposal and the sample collection method employed. Moisture content helps in determining the possibility of fugitive dust problem during material handling and transportation.

The volatile matter content in DTPS sample (4.9%) is greater that BTPS fly ash (2.44%). The ash percentage of BTPS ash (88.61%) is much more than DTPS fly ash (75.81%) and therefore fixed carbon (18.58%) and LOI (24.19%) of DTPS fly ash is greater that BTPS fly ash

for which these values are 7.52% and 11.39% respectively.

Purpose of this study was to investigate the flotation behavior of unburnt carbon in a Denver type flotation machine. The feasibility of separating unburnt carbon and ash was determined. The results indicate that it is effective in removing the unburnt carbon from fly ash which can be attributed to the generation of bubbles and continuous circulation method under the optimized conditions, BTPS fly ash with 11.39% LOI and 7.52% fixed carbon and DTPS fly ash with 24.19% LOI and 18.58% fixed carbon recovered. It enables unburnt carbon of fly ash to be recovered and reused in other applications.

Discussion on froth flotation method :

In the present investigation, collector and frother dosages have been considered as the main variables while all other variables were kept constant. The effect of reagent dosages is summarized in the following sections :

Effect of collector and frother dosages on BTPS fly ash sample :

Effect of collector dosage :

Fig. 3 depicts the collector dosage plotted against carbon recovery at 0.25, 0.50, 0.75 and 1.00 kg/ton of frother levels. In this analysis, carbon recovery has been calculated using the following equation :

$$R = Y * [(100 - (c + M + Vm)) / [100 - (f + M + Vm)]] \quad (1)$$

where, c and f indicate the ash percentages of concentrate

Fig. 3. Effect of collector dosage on carbon recovery of BTPS fly ash.

and feed respectively; Y is the yield of concentrate in percentage and M and Vm indicate the moisture a volatile matter percentage in feed and concentrate respectively.

It can be clearly observed from the figure that for the experiments performed at a fixed level of frother dosage of 0.25 kg/ton, with increase in collector dosage from 1.0 to 1.75 kg/ton, carbon recovery increases gradually.

When the frother dosage is fixed at 0.50 kg/ton, with increase in collector dosage from 1 to 1.25 kg/ton, carbon recovery decreases and then rises gently at 1.5 kg/ton and again declines with increase in collector dosage to 1.75 kg/ton. Therefore, at 0.50 kg/ton of frother dosage, maximum yield is obtained when collector dosage is 1.5 kg/ton.

Whereas for a fixed frother dosage 0.75 kg/ton, for the increase of collector dosage from 1.0 to 1.75 kg/ton, the carbon recovery pattern is almost similar to the plot as observed at constant dosage of 0.25 kg/ton i.e. it shows a gradual and continuous increase. The maximum recovery of carbon is obtained at the collector dosage of 1.75 kg/ton. Lastly when the frother dosage is fixed at 1.0 kg/ton there is a decrease in the recovery of carbon from collector dosage 1.0 to 1.75 kg/ton. It can be seen from the figure that maximum carbon recovery is obtained at a collector dosage of 1 kg/ton.

Effect of frother dosage :

To analyze the influence of frother dosages keeping collector dosage level to be constant, Fig. 4 has been plotted on the figure, the frother dosage levels have been plotted against percentage of carbon recovery. It can be

noted from the nature of the curves that in most cases with increase in frother dosage, the recovery of carbon does not show any definite trend, which may again be because of the interactional effects of collector and frother dosages. The reasons for the above type of variations may be attributed to the interactional effects that exist between collector and frothers and these dosages added, which is very difficult to conclude at this juncture.

For example at collector level 1.0 kg/ton, the recovery of carbon first increases, then decreases and finally increases abruptly and goes to a maximum value at the frother dosage of 1.0 kg/ton. At collector level 1.25 kg/ton, the carbon recovery increases gradually with increase in frother dosage. However, from the results one remarkable point to be noted is at 1.75 kg/ton, the graph is just the reverse of that obtained at 1.0 kg/ton. It can also be noticed from this figure that maximum yield is obtained with the flotation test condition of collector dosage 1 kg/ton and frother level 1 kg/ton, these dosages are reasonably high.

Hence a proper selection of flotation test condition can be made only after a scrutiny of ash values and economics.

Effect of collector and frother dosage on DTPS fly ash sample :

Effect of collector dosages :

Results obtained for the carbon recovering from DTPS fly ash at different collector dosages are presented in the Fig. 5 considering collector abscissas plotted against carbon recovery on ordinate at constant frother level of 0.75, 1.00, 1.25 and 1.50 kg/ton respectively.

Fig. 4. Effect of frother dosage on carbon recovery of BTPS fly ash.

Fig. 5. Effect of collector dosage on carbon recovery of DTPS fly ash.

In this plot, there exists a definite relationship among all the four plots. A general decreasing trend in the carbon recovery from an initial high value with increases in collector dosage can be noticed. This variable is clearly noted for the experiments carried out with lowest frother dosages of 0.75 kg/ton but at times this decrease trend deviates in the plots.

The highest recovery is obtained at 1.50 kg/ton of frother dosage and 1.50 kg/ton of collector dosage.

In Fig. 6, the frother dosage levels have been plotted against carbon recovery percentage at constant collector dosage. The plot obtained at constant collector dosage

1.50 kg/ton is almost similar to that of the 1.75 kg/ton, and the plot obtained at collector dosage 2.00 kg/ton is almost similar to 2.25 kg/ton. However the maximum carbon recovery is obtained corresponding to collector dosage 1.50 kg/ton and frother dosage 1.50 kg/ton.

Analysis of flotation performances :

To analyze the separation efficiency of flotation process for recovery of carbonaceous material, the following methodology has been adopted; separation efficiency has been considered as the numerical difference of recoveries of carbonaceous material and the ash material in the froth products.

Fig. 6. Effect of frother dosage on carbon recovery of DTPS fly ash.

This means that when the recovery of carbonaceous material is high with minimal ash recovery, the value of separation efficiency (SE) will also be high. Suppose if the recovery of carbonaceous material is constant but if the recovery of ash is high, this means that the separation efficiency (SE) will be poor and it may become negative also indicating recovery of ash to be higher than the carbonaceous material. If both the recoveries are increasing simultaneously, means none of these components (either ash or non-ash) are floating preferentially and the froth product grade remains similar to that of feed. Hence use of this approach will indicate the true efficiency of separation for the recovery of carbonaceous material.

The formula for the estimation of SE can be written as

$$SE = R_c - R_a \quad (2)$$

where SE is the value of separation efficiency, and R_c is the recovery of carbonaceous material and R_a is the recovery of ash material.

The value of R_a in eq. (2) has been estimated using the formula

$$R_a = \frac{\text{Yield} \times \text{Ash percentage of the froth product}}{\text{Ash percentage of the feed sample}}$$

Prediction of separation efficiency :

It can be said that the effect of frother dosage is found to be predominant in case of both BTPS and DTPS samples, when compared to the effect of the collector

dosage, kerosene oil, on the separation efficiency of carbonaceous material using fly ash. Besides this in both the cases, the interactional effects of collector and frother show least significance. Estimating percent standard deviation values, which are found to be 12.65% and 12.21% for BTPS and DTPS respectively, has made the goodness of above equation.

Conclusion

In case of froth flotation, it was concluded from the above results that dosage of reagents play a major role in the carbon recovery by froth flotation method. The irregularities found in the curves are due to interaction between the collector and frother. In case of BTPS fly ash, 73% of carbon recovery has been found while in DTPS fly ash the maximum recovery is only 43.97%.

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